

A Human and Energy Perspective on the Relationship between Physiological Balance and Nutrition with the Effect of the Illusion of Motion Through the Virtual Labyrinth and the Experience of the "Out of Body" Phenomenon in Virtual Reality (VR)

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Abstract

Researchers found an association between higher levels of brain activity in the right and left DLPFC and a reduced sense of presence (Baumgartner et al., 2008). Thus, the correct DLPFC influences the "presence effect" experience by controlling the flow of visual information processed in posterior parietal brain regions. These regions handle assessing the feeling of one's own body (or part of it) outdoors. To counter this, the left lateral prefrontal cortex has a connection with the

medial prefrontal cortex, which takes part in the regulation of self-reflection activity and "inwardly directed streams of consciousness." This allows the left lateral prefrontal cortex to influence the quality and intensity of the presence experience (Baumgartner et al., 2008). It is interesting to note that children between the ages of 6 and 11 tend to be more fully immersed in virtual reality than adults. Baumgartner et al. (2008), long patterns of maturation of the prefrontal cortex during postnatal development may supply a plausible explanation for this fact. This finding was published in the journal Nature Neuroscience. Numerous studies investigating the presence effect associated with experiencing the illusion of motion through the virtual labyrinth (vection illusion) and the "out-of-body" phenomenon in virtual reality (VR) have uncovered brain mechanisms. Coordination between the proprioceptive, visual and vestibular systems in the process of perceiving one's own body (Costantini, Haggard, 2007; Ehrsson, 2007, 2009), as well as space and spatial orientation (the question of the role played by Keshava Multimodal stimulation). It appeared because of studies devoted to the phenomenon in the formation of subjective feelings about the "physical self" (body) and, more broadly, in the formation of "self-reflection" and "self-consciousness" mechanisms. new forms of therapy based on virtual out-of-body experience and virtual exposure methods make extensive use of the person's ability to immerse themselves in a virtual environment (Muhlberger, Pauli, 2011).

Keywords: *Virtual Maze, Illusion of Vection, Illusion of Motion, In Virtual Reality (VR), "Out of Body" Phenomenon, Physiological Balance, Human and Its Energy in Nutrition Relationship*

1. Introduction

The use of a virtual environment as an instrumental framework for behavioral therapy to treat phobias, fears, post-traumatic disorders, drug addiction, and stress-related illnesses (Selisskaya et al., 2004; Hoffman, 2004; Voiskunsky, Menshikova, 2008; Ignatiev et al., 2009). It has been difficult to obtain comprehensive knowledge of the role nutrition plays in the development of obesity, as it has been difficult to gather helpful reviews of food consumption in people who are free to live their lives freely. Obese individuals tend to under-report the amount of food they consume by as much as thirty percent (Lichtman et al. 1992), and most obese individuals are

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believed to consume more calories than lean individuals (when paired for exercise and other things. This is in addition to the obvious effect of the availability of palatable food on body weight). Because the concept of energy balance is fundamental, the only context in which a person's dietary intake may be considered inadequate or excessive has to do with the amount of energy they spend. It is noticeably clear that various people have varying degrees of inherited predisposition to hold excessive caloric intake as fat. In a seminal study, Bouchard and colleagues experimented with overfeeding monozygotic twins in carefully measured amounts (Bouchard et al. 1990). However, the trend for increased adiposity in each pair of twins was quite similar. This is even though diverse groups of twins differ significantly in the extent to which these calories are stored as adipose tissue as fat. Because overfeeding was controlled above basic needs, the possible difference in fat accumulation between the twin groups was likely due to differences in some components of energy expenditure, possibly basal metabolic rates or adaptive thermogenesis . This was because overfeeding was controlled over basic needs. Prospective studies conducted in Pima Indians (Ravussin 1995) , a Native American population with a strong propensity for obesity, supply further evidence that changes in metabolic rate are crucial determinants of human obesity. Pima Indigenous people have a high tendency to be overweight. When people were categorized by their metabolic rate and then checked, those with slower metabolic rates had higher prevalence and severity of obesity.

2. CNS Management of One's Energy Consumption and One's Weight

The activity of the autonomic nervous system, which regulates energy expenditure and other aspects of metabolism, is influenced by the central nervous system (CNS), which has three effects:

- a. *effects on behavior, including eating and physical activity.*
- b. *effects on the activity of the autonomic nervous system, which regulates energy consumption and other aspects of metabolism; and*
- c. *effects on the neuroendocrine system, including the secretion of hormones such as growth hormone, thyroid , cortisol, insulin, and sex steroids*

3. Controlling the Amount of Energy Consumed in Both the Short and Long Term

The act of feeding lies at the intersection of free choice and physiology and is greatly influenced by a variety of different conditions. In addition to the availability of food, eating is affected by factors related to metabolism, the nervous system, and the endocrine system. It can also be changed by intense sensory, olfactory, emotional and mental input. As a result, it is necessary to take all these aspects into account to conclude about when the feeding intervals will begin and end (Schwartz et al. 2000). Both short-term and long-term control mechanisms are possible in the context of regulation of eating behavior. The beginning and end of mealtimes are essential components of short-term regulation. The onset of satiety, which is a response to neural and endocrine factors such as bowel distention and secretion of the intestinal peptide cholecystokinin (CCK), produced during meal intake, is the primary factor deciding the amount of food. Meal size can also be affected by other factors such as hunger (Moran 2000). These signals are then sent via the vagus nerve to the caudal brainstem , where integration with other inputs occurs , resulting in the end of the meal. Because mice repeatedly injected with CCK maintain their weight by eating more food at a smaller size, regulation of individual meal size by the variables produced by eating is insufficient to account for energy balance over extended periods of time. Long-term signals reflecting the state of energy storage, such as the hormone leptin produced from fat , provide the central nervous system with information that further controls eating behavior to keep energy balance. These short-term and long-term systems are interconnected, and this should come as no surprise (Emond et al. 1999). Consequently, the nutritional response to energy deficiency is mostly driven by increased meal size. Methods in the field of psychophysiology are increasingly used in psychotherapy sessions and to decide how effective they are (Hoffman 2004; Cornwell et al. 2006; Galatenko et al. 2012; Lobacheva et al. 2013). When modeling and researching complex social phenomena (n virtual environments) such as inter-ethnic interactions, objective psychophysiological control of presence influence is extremely important. Approaches from the field of psychophysiology to the study of social cognition and social behavior Psychophysiology studies that explore the mechanics behind social perception (also known as "Brain Reading" and "Theory of Mind"):

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*mirror neurons, emotional resonance , cognitive resonance and gnostic neurons of face
recognition and recognition of emotional facial expressions*

In the field of neuroscience and psychophysiology, an autonomous scientific movement has appeared over the past decade. Examination of the cognitive bases of human relationships and interactions (Hari , 2002; Shen , Liu, Yuan, 2011). There are academic publications, monographs, and tutorials devoted to the concerns of social neuroscience ("SCAN"; "J. of Social Neuroscience ", "J. of cognitive Neuroscience ", "J. Human Brain Mapping " and "J. culture and Brain"), as noted earlier, the signs of personification in a society include social conversation and people's biological uniqueness, both of which are necessary but not sufficient on their own. Another need is to set up their own identity between a single person and other members of the community viewed as distinct individuals. It is the existence of "individual" bonds that express connections that can be made with their external appearance and "inner world." This psychophysiological personification initially manifests itself in monkeys but reaches its highest development in humans. Due to their elevated level of development, people can see and judge the inner worlds of others as different from their own. In the communication process, the assessment of the psychological state of a partner is based on various information about the individual. This assessment is based on the individual's physical identity, the nature of limbs and body movements (postures, gestures), facial expressions, and specific features of vocalization. These information processing activities have been gathered under the umbrella term "social cognition", sometimes also known as "social perception (intelligence)". Certain mechanisms have evolved over the course of evolution to create individualized communities within the nervous systems of social animals . These mechanisms handle keeping social awareness and selectively responding to social inputs.

Studies conducted in the fields of physiological and neuropsychological research in the 21st century have found various categories of socially oriented neural mechanisms. Some are localized in the central nervous system and

- 1) *acoustic signal complexes (responsible for speech in humans),*
- 2) *gestures and poses and*
- 3) *associated with certain social signals, such as emotional facial expressions.*

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Other processes lie around the nervous system and depend on the autonomic nervous system's unique adaptations to support social behavior (Blascovich , 2000). Mimetic muscles are a unique set of facial muscles that developed during the development of mammals. These muscles allow higher animals to communicate their emotions through nonverbal communication. These muscles in the animal's skin manage a wide variety of tasks , including regulating the movements of the animal's whiskers and ears, producing various auditory signals, and creating emotional facial expressions. Charles Darwin believed that the movements of the facial muscles and certain ritualized movements of the extremities (or possibly the whole body) could be seen as an alphabet of this emotional language, a form of emotional gesture.

The motor cortex area responsible for controlling facial muscles is significantly larger than the area responsible for regulating hand movements. This is because of the importance of mimetic muscles for human behavior . Some scholars believe that there are some "basic" emotions that can be recognized at once by facial expression and that these emotions can be considered as social signals in the nonverbal (emotional) communication channel (Izard , 1980; Ekman , 2010). The presence of such motivating emotional communication signals shows the existence of certain mechanisms within the nervous system that manage their creation and recognition. Indeed, recent neurophysiological studies of the brains of primates and humans have shown that the temporal cortex and amygdala are used for the identification of facial expressions and emotions. indicates the existence of specific neural pathways (Jankowski , Takahashi , 2014).

When the structure is damaged, there is a natural deterioration in social relations, and it is possible that the neurons in the amygdala responsible for emotional facial expressions are also part of the system that regulates social relations . For example, in a hierarchically ordered ape society, power can change suddenly and drastically (Pribram , 1975). Clinical observations supplied further evidence to support psychophysiological research findings on social feeling. Therefore, when a person sustains a bilateral lesion in the occipitotemporal cortex, they may develop the neurological facial agnosia syndrome , also known as prosopagnosia . This is the inability to recognize both familiar and unfamiliar faces in conjunction with a completely undamaged state of all other cognitive brain functions. In addition to losing the ability to recognize certain individuals, patients with this syndrome continue to correctly interpret the emotional expressions of others, even if they

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do so impersonally (for example, "someone is crying", "someone is laughing"). This is one of the hallmarks of this syndrome .

G. Kliiver and P. Bucy in 1937 in both affected animals (Kliiver-Bucy syndrome) described a symptom of behavioral disturbance in higher mammals following bilateral lesions of the temporal anterior lobe. This condition is characterized by several main symptoms , the most obvious of which are hypersexuality , excessive attention, and unreasonable worry . Other symptoms include hyperorality and hypersexuality (distortion of emotions or reduced emotional impact, feeling violated, distorted feeling of the emotional meaning of signals) , in which a person investigates by putting things in their mouth . Later researchers, Kliiver-Bucy They found that changes in emotional state, such as those seen in patients with the syndrome , were linked to damage to the amygdala , and the extent to which different animals were affected by such disruptions varied greatly. As a result, after the amygdala is removed, cats turn into extremely aggressive creatures (undomesticated, ape-like). In this way, the clinical data confirm the psychophysiological data on the leading role of neurons in the temporal cortex and neurons in the amygdala in the perception (recognition) of faces (ie, the perception of emotional facial expressions). Gnostic facial neurons, also known as "neuron sensors of a person" and "neuron sensors of emotional facial expressions", are components of the neurophysiological system known as the "Who" system. This system integrates information about other people. The purpose of the "Who" system developed in phylogeny was to fulfill the important task of enabling individuals to interpret various kinds of information (including their psychological states) about other individuals and ultimately to determine their dispositions.

Damage to the brain systems used to recognize people and facial expressions are fundamental processes of social cognition. If these mechanisms are damaged, it can lead to the loss of the entire system of social cohesion. from the University of Parma (Universita ' degli in Italy) studio di Parma) researchers conducted neurophysiological experiments with macaques in the late 20th century. As a result of these experiments, the researchers discovered what are now known as mirror neurons (MNs) in the lower part of the frontal cortex (field F5 analogue n. 44 in humans) (Galese et al., 1996). MNs were activated both when the monkey was performing certain actions and when the monkey was controlling the experimenter performing the same actions.

4. Duties of the Hypothalamus

Duties of the Hypothalamus is an area of the brain that plays a key role in the control of homeostatic activities, including reproduction, thermoregulation, and eating (Elmqvist et al. 1999). The hypothalamus manages sensing signals from the brain, endocrine and metabolic systems, integrating these inputs, and activating various effector pathways that ultimately result in responses from the behavioral, autonomic and endocrine systems. In addition to the hypothalamus, neuronal circuits widely distributed in the brainstem, cerebral cortex, olfactory regions, and other parts of the body take part in the central regulation of hunger and maintenance of energy balance. The lesion experiments were crucial in deciding at an early stage the essential function played by the hypothalamus in both hunger and satiety. Lesions in the ventromedial hypothalamus handle obesity, and lesions in the lateral hypothalamus handle weakness (Elmqvist et al. 1999). However, interpretation of this paradigm was limited by the inherent immaturity of physical injuries and the lack of established molecular and anatomical pathways underlying them; Therefore, different techniques were tried. For example, researchers investigated the effects of centrally delivered neurotransmitters such as norepinephrine, dopamine, and serotonin, as well as hypothalamic neuropeptides such as NPY and CRH, on food intake, autonomic output, metabolic rate, and energy balance. According to the findings of these studies, the central nervous system has many ligand-receptor pathways that can affect energy intake, energy balance and metabolic status.

5. Initial Research on NPY

Neuropeptide Y (NPY) pathway is the most representative example of such research. NPY is widely and abundantly expressed throughout the neurological system. The arcuate nucleus of the hypothalamus is one of the most intense expression areas and is recognized only where nutritional control (intensified by famine) occurs. When neuropeptide Y (NPY) is injected into the cerebral ventricles or some hypothalamic nuclei, it causes strong and rapid increases in eating, while reducing the amount of energy spent, leading to the development of obesity (Stanley et al. 1986).

, Billington et al. 1994). Therefore, NPY was considered a strong competitor for an endogenous regulator of energy balance, due to its ability to stimulate anabolism in response to energy deficiencies. Our limited understanding of the physiological system in which these powerful neural circuits are involved was the largest knowledge gap when it comes to NPY and many other neurochemicals that have similarly been shown to stimulate or suppress feeding. This was also true for most other neurochemicals. More specifically, how did nutritional status communicate information to these central pathways so that it could be integrated and controlled? Insulin, a hormone, was an obvious competitor for the role of signaling (Schwartz et al. 2000). When a person is starving, their insulin levels go down, but when they're obese, their insulin levels go up. Insulin levels reflect energy balance and reserves. Insulin reduces both food intake and curved NPY expression when administered centrally. This is because insulin enters the brain through a saturable mechanism and reaches its maximum ability there. On the other hand, insulin deficiency, as in type 1 diabetes, is more linked to weight loss than weight gain. Additionally, due to the lack of evidence that physiological shifts in peripheral insulin levels affect energy balance via the brain, most researchers concluded that insulin is not the primary peripheral signal delivered to the CNS for purpose. regulation of energy balance. This signal had not yet been discovered at that point.

6. The Same Neurons in Our Brain Are Activated When We Execute Similar Types Of Activities On Our Own

Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), positron emission tomography (PET), magnetoencephalography (MEG), and electroencephalography (EEG), several separate research teams have concluded that certain areas of the human cerebral cortex are activated. Premotor cortex and inferior parietal In addition to the gyrus, MNs cingulate It has been shown that it can also be found in the gyrus, somatosensory cortex, and insula. All these regions are part of the limbic system (Blakemore et al., 2005; Liepelt et al., 2009). of MN Because of its discovery, it is now possible to give a clear answer to the question of why in certain situations we can understand other people's actions so easily and quickly. It is generally accepted that when we see another

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person's movements, the same neurons in our brain are active when we carry out similar types of activities on our own.

As a result, we can sense what the other person is doing and predict the continuation and fulfillment of their activities without having to go through any complex logical calculations. The discovery of MNs marked the beginning of an innovative approach in the fields of neuroscience and psychophysiology, variously called "Brain Reading" or "Theory of Mind." Data obtained in its framework proved the involvement of the brain in the organization of social interaction (learning communication skills, predicting the behavior of the communication partner), emotional empathy processes, and the evolution of communication systems (from poses) (Baars , Gage , 2010; Rizzolatti , Sinigaglia , 2008—English, Oxford Press). , 2006 Italian , Raffaello Cortina).

There is evidence from experiments suggesting that MN disruption may be a cause of autism in infants (Ramachandran , 2014). Specifically, this hypothesis supplies an explanation for certain autistic traits. These traits include a desire to isolate oneself from the outside world and avoid social interactions, difficulties in understanding and simulating the actions and emotions of others, and insensitivity to other people's feelings. The unique activity of the brain in terms of direct social interaction (joint actions, communication) is one of the most important topics for social psychophysiology and cognitive sciences:

Is such a thing happening? If so, what exactly does it work? To find an answer to this issue, the TV Chernigovskaya group developed an innovative interdisciplinary strategy based on a mix of research techniques from neurophysiology, psychology and linguistics (Chernigovskaya , 2007).

Electroencephalograms (EEGs) of two test participants working together to solve cognitive tasks (including visual-spatial orientation) under environments of active social interaction were analyzed by the researchers (discussion). The idea behind this concept was that simultaneous activation of several communication partners in the brain is necessary for cooperative social actions to occur. The authors showed that in solving cognitive problems in the context of social interaction, the following activities were seen among subjects:

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- (1) *synchronization of electrical activity in the parietal region of the left hemisphere and*
- (2) *general changes. frontal interhemispheric asymmetry , characteristic for emotional support of communication , in the EEG.*

These findings lend credence to the hypothesis that prefrontal cortex, temporal lobe, and temporoparietal junction structures are important for social communication. This hypothesis has been extensively discussed in the scientific literature . It is important to note that the highest temporal matching achieved in the partners' EEGs throughout the communication process occurs when the problem solving (social interaction) process is running at its highest efficiency. The authors attributed the predominance of EEG synchronization in the parietal region of the left hemisphere to the formation of the "general focus of attention in the system" during the interaction process. ("From physiological psychology to psychological physiology ...") This process included problem solving and communication environment. It also included interactions between partners themselves. By combining data from synchronization of brain activity with data from psychological and linguistic analysis of interactions between partners in the problem-solving process, the authors were able to conceptualize a new psychophysiological phenomenon called cognitive resonance .

This phenomenon is a special complement to another phenomenon that is extremely important to social relations. This other phenomenon is the phenomenon of emotional resonance, which is associated with the establishment of emotional interaction (harmony) of partners in communication. This phenomenon is a special complement to the other phenomenon.

7. Personal Distancing Mechanisms

The mechanisms of keeping "personal distance" in communication between members of the personified community governed by psychological and physiological processes should not be surprising, with people having to share living space (communication). However, why can it be difficult for us at times, even the presence of our closest and dearest, who are always by our side? Also, why do we dislike intruding into our private worlds? Why does each of us have something

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called a "drive" that causes us to be only accessible and to a certain degree "open to others"? Why is it necessary for people to "keep a certain distance" from each other? A comparison between human societies and biological communities in which community life is not combined with an individual's keeping of distance may help us understand the origin of the need to "keep individual distance" . ("From physiological psychology to psychological physiology ...") Collective living in biological communities is not combined with the individual's distancing. Having an innate drive for individual freedom combined with the need for cohabitation, cohabitation or co-dwelling is unusual for all species. It is conspicuously absent in insect communities; bees living in the hive physiologically feel comfortable with each other (i.e., touching). There is no evidence that fish are afraid of being touched in any way. A flock of fish gathers into a solid mass. Animals in rat families are always social and always open to close, physical contact with one another. What binds these communities together? Animals such as insects, fish, and mice do not have personalities. All people are comparable to each other and can find each other based on basic characteristics shared by all members of the group (i.e., based on the concept of "friend-or foe"). In contrast to such anonymous and anonymous organizations, human societies are personified, and each member of a community has its own unique "collection of important characteristics" (individuality).

Individual distance can be expressed as the distance between people that allows the person to defend himself more effectively if attacked by a partner . Research on monkeys to explore the neurophysiology of mirror neurons has revealed that these neurons take part in processes underlying deliberate action, particularly activity that serves to keep individual distance (Thill , Svensson , Ziemke , 2011). There is some evidence that humans still show territorial behavior. For example, we involuntarily get angry when we must wait in line in a busy place, and the person feels uncomfortable when left alone. Animals, like humans, have their own sense of physical "I" that includes their own bodies, their own territory, and sometimes even their own close relatives who are carriers of the genes they share. The inner need to sustain all this can be seen as the Tekstovoe pole: a manifestation of the instinctive longing to be free. IP Pavlov was the first to use this expression after seeing dogs unable to learn a new skill due to high enthusiasm. These dogs constantly fought on a leash, as they could not stand confinement. This inspired Pavlov to coin the term. Humans also have a freedom reflex, but it doesn't just occur in response to physical

confinement; rather, it arises in response to the conceptual violation of '1'. Shown aggression (anger), genuine aggression (attack), and selective behavioral responses are examples of self-protection (keeping personal distance) by "keeping distance" (fear).

8. Leptin and Monogenic Obesity Case

Cloning the genetic loci responsible for many of the previously described monogenic obesity syndromes in mice was a huge step forward for the science of energy balance, which has seen rapid progress as a result. The discovery that ob / ob and db / db mouse strains have a genetic predisposition to develop obesity disorders has led to some of the most important and far-reaching advances in this field (Zhang et al 1994, Chen et al 1996). Earlier research had used the parabiosis method, in which mice would be surgically linked together to allow for the transfer of molecules from one mouse to another . Thus, it was hypothesized thirty years ago that ob / ob mice do not have a circulating satiety signal, while db / db mice may lack its equivalent receptor. This led to the conclusion that both types of mice could be obese. With the successful cloning of these genes in 1994 and 1995 , this insightful prognosis was shown to be correct. Leptin gets its name from the Greek word leptos , which literally means "thin" . (“Strategies for Achieving Satiety”) The ob gene handles encoding this one-of-a-kind cytokine. The adipocyte is the primary site where leptin is released, and mutant animals have proteins that are shortened and physiologically inactive as a result (Zhang et al. 1994). Treatment of the hormone absent in ob / ob mice can reverse the development of the obesity syndrome (Halaas et al. 1995, Friedman and Halaas 1998). There are reports of upregulated expression of leptin in added regions such as skeletal muscle (Wang et al. 1998), placenta, and stomach . While it has not yet been confirmed whether these expressions have a physiological meaning , it is likely to be in the future . The leptin receptor ObRb As a result of deletion of the signaling form in db / db mice (Chen et al. 1996, Friedman and Halaas 1998), these animals are insensitive to both endogenous and exogenous leptin . The discovery of these two proteins lays the groundwork for the first well-documented components of a powerful nutritional feedback loop from adipose tissue to the brain.

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Creative activity is another expressive technique and "self- protection against slavery" (Brodsky , 1987), in addition to defensive reflexes as a way of protecting one's identity. The following questions about keeping individual distance (personal space) are still subject to further research and analysis.

- 1) *does the need to stay away from other individuals first arise in the animal kingdom ?*
- 2) *Why is there a desire to preserve a certain amount of space in certain situations (even among close relatives) but not in others (even with complete strangers)?*
- 3) *Do diverse cultures make different attempts to stay away from each other?*

yes , what are the main processes that cause these cultural differences? Methods based on psychophysiology were used to investigate cultural differences. The term "cultural neuroscience" refers to new lines of research into the connections that exist between the brain and diverse cultures. Currently, the question of whether there is a link between social relations and neuroscience is not uncommon and not unrelated to basic research. Experimental studies of the connection between the brain and economics (neuroeconomics), the brain and politics (biopolitics), the brain and art (neuroaesthetics), and more generally the brain and human culture (cultural neuroscience) are gaining momentum in the modern world. neuroscience and psychophysiology, found at the intersection of psychology , neuroscience, cultural anthropology, and genetics. Such research is of interest at the intersection of psychology, neuroscience, cultural anthropology, and genetics (Falikman , Cole , 2014; Zhou, Cacioppo, 2010; Kitayama , Uskul , 2011; LeClair , Janusonis , Kim, 2014). Studies on the relationship between brain plasticity and the acquisition of various cultural experiences and the physiological drivers of cognitive processes in various cultures are conducted in the light of these new lines of research (Millar et al., 2013; Kelkar , Hough). , Fang , 2013). The concepts of social neuroscience and social psychophysiology easily converge with theories of the existence of brain structures, the substrate of social functions internalized throughout the process of evolution and ontogenesis .

Brain and social classification process The investigation of the mechanisms of "social categorization", the perception of the social environment as categories of group membership and position in the social structure, is a mainstream neurocognitive and psychophysiological research.

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the study of cultural phenomena. This study examines how certain behavioral expectations are associated with group membership and position categories in social structure (Contreras , Banaji , Mitchell, 2011). Findings of modern social psychophysiology provide evidence that the brain specializes in connection with processes of social categorization that have made an important contribution to the development of Homo sapiens (Kinzler , Spelke , 2007). Relationship between the brain and social perception , including attitudes towards various social groups and socially oriented information There is evidence (EEG, fMRI, PET) that there is a statistically significant difference in human brain responses when perceiving different social groups. including representatives of one's own and an "alien" social group (Rilling et al., 2008; Volz , Kessler, von Gramon , 2009; Vrticka et al. 2009; Van Bavel , Packer , Cunningham, 2008), (Knutson e (Freeman et al ., 2010). In this and many other studies, it has been shown that the perception of different social categories involves the same regions of the brain. Cultural distinctions in the processes involved in social cognition are also shown (Ng et al., 2010; Harada, Chiao , 2010) Many important breakthroughs have been made in the field of social psychology in examining how individuals from collectivist and individualistic cultures view each other . Psychophysiological methods for the study of social categorization processes such as racial perception, stereotypes, and prejudices have been extensively researched. In the field of social neuroscience, the study of stereotypes and prejudices as well as racial perception attracts the most attention when discussing social classification procedures (Ito , Bartholow , 2009; Dickter , Bartholow , 2007; Knutson et al. al ., 2007). Because of the practical importance of this topic in the United States, most research on this topic is conducted in that country. Thus, the first groundbreaking study showed that the amygdala , which is often linked to a response to emotionally significant stimuli, plays a role in the feeling of individuals of different races (Hart et al, 2000; Phelps et al, 2000).

Research led by Cunningham and colleagues (Cunningham et al., 2004) proved the relevance of neuroscience research for understanding cognitive processes involved in perceiving people of one's own race, as well as other races:

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When the stimulus exposure time was greater than the conscious feeling threshold (0.5 s), there was no rapid activation of the amygdala in response to the unconscious display of people of other races.

This finding, which can be interpreted because of suppression of the automatic stereotyped response by controlled processes, was seen when the exposure time to the stimulus 30 milliseconds was. Golby et al. (2001), Richeson et al. (2003), Lieberman et al. (2005), Adams et al. (2009), Bruneau and Saxe (2010), Xu et al. (2009), Cheon et al. (2011) and Losin et al. (2012), the differential response of the human brain to the exposure of representatives of an individual's race and/or ethnic group during the performance of different experiments (Kurzban , Cosmides , 2001). On the other hand, research on the neurophysiological basis of social cognition is only just beginning to gain momentum, even though there is a great lack of methodological consistency. Therefore, limited brain ability is not supported by either traditional neurophysiology or contemporary neuroscience. This applies to even the most basic physiological (like breathing) and psychological (attention, memory, emotions, speech, feeling) activities.

9. Conclusion

In the case of feeling and recognition of faces only, such specialization is consistently reflected when considering socially charged categories (temporal cortex and adjacent amygdala). From the perspective of an experimental neuropsychologist , the task of finding brain correlates (patterns of brain activity) for invaluable categories of stimuli such as "marital status", "political relationship" or "social hierarchy" appears to be inadequate. In this context, what is the main difference between the proposed research projects and an earlier study conducted by F. Gall that investigated the location of various personality traits (in the brain) such as "independence", "amor patriae "? The proposed meta-analysis method in this area (analysis of data obtained in the framework of socially oriented neurophysiological research by various authors) accumulated little statistically significant material and was contaminated with "noisy" differences. in terms of specific experiments performed (Van Overwalle , 2009). The terms functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and positron emission tomography (PET) are often used in meta-analyses conducted in contemporary

neuroscience and psychophysiology. To begin with, the study of tomograms is a type of statistical analysis and therefore has certain limitations about the precision and reliability of data on the location of brain activity patterns. Second, fMRI and PET cannot find the type of physiological processes (excitation/inhibition) occurring at active sites and do not allow detection of functioning areas with low energy requirements. In addition, these techniques do not allow detecting functioning areas.

10. References

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